
THE BAD SIDE OF TRADE OPENNESS AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: PRE & POST TRADE LIBERALIZATION PERIOD**Mr. Ashis Kumarsa**

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Abstract- The industrial revolution in the European nation has started first, then it spread to the American nation, much latter spread to the developing nations like India. Due to the industrial revolution high rate of economic growth is induced, increasing per capita income and higher standard of living is the product of high growth. No doubt the unprecedented population growth & the increased income of people have to indulge in different luxurious or different other than necessary consumption, accordingly to full fill the demand output must be increased which shows the depletion of natural resources and other degradation like climate change (due to CO₂ emission) and ozone layer depletion. In the twentieth century, these problem along with scarcity of natural resources are seems to be a global problem. After the emergence of WTO in 1995 with the goal of free flow of goods and services, no doubt the efficient utilization of resources taking place globally, if we talk about the trade restrictions it might be erroneous in this time. But the completely free flow of goods and services is loss for the developing country because the advanced nations have raised their standard of living at the cost of their environment, now it is time for the developing nations to raise their standard of living at their cost of own environment if but the development of the European nations and American nation were at the time where there were no conscious about the environmental issues like mentioned above but the developing country should learn from this lesson and restrict their trade openness because the trade openness gives rise to higher economic growth and consequently the degradation of environment. Because higher income leads to increase in the luxurious consumption and production of this types of commodity generates huge wastage. At the same time the countries have to achieve the environmental targets set for sustainable development so both phenomenon is moving in a different direction. So endeavor of the study is to show the relation between the trade, growth and CO₂ before and after trade liberalization and their trends by which we can conclude about why there should be trade restrictions in developing countries.

Keywords: Environmental degradation, trade volume, economic growth, GDP per capita, CO₂ Emission, economic development, advanced nation, trade openness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The gradual process of industrial revolution (which can be termed as economic growth) has led to serious environmental impacts on the ecology and environment causing severe natural hazards, depletion of ozone layer, the climate change. These are the result of increasing emission of the GHGs and other toxic gases (CFC, CO₂, CO, SO, NO, NO₂). As a result the advanced nations are forced to step towards reforms and finally watershed moment came as 1972 Stockholm convention the UNCHE the product was UNEP, and the decennial meeting in 1992 earth summit, the Paris agreement 2015 for controlling the anthropogenic activity for the simulations of sustainable development. The montreal

protocol for controlling the depletion of ozone layer in 1987 etc.

We can see a strong correlation between economic growth, international trade openness and the environmental degradation (between GDP per capita, Trade volume and CO₂ emission). So for degradation of the environment the economic growth is a main factor, certain study says the 95% of species have gone extinct since humanity became the dominant species in the earth, and in the eighteenth century the trade between European nations and rest all shows high economic growth in the former due to increasing volume of trade. So in the study we will get to know some part of the environmental Degradation is caused by the international trade and especially

export which induces high production and degradation of resources, because it induces high growth that means high cost for environment.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the study is to show the relation between the three variables, GDP_{PPP} per capita, CO₂ emission, and Trade volume which are representing the rate of economic growth, the environmental degradation, and the trade openness respectively. This is to prove that the international trade also causes CO₂ to rise and what cost the country needs in terms of environment to maintain sustainable development with open trade is greater than the restrictive trade situations. The study will show that trade increases the income (GDP_{PPP} pc) and the increased income needs more goods and services to meet the increasing demand. And finally the increased demand is more of a comfort or luxury goods than necessity. Hence the trade increases Environmental degradation.

3. EMERGENCE OF THE STUDY

This is the proper time for the developing nations for realizing that they have the potential to realize the targets set by different international environmental conventions for simulations of sustainable development mentioned above, due to comparatively lower technological progress the extraction was not so high of the natural resources. The developing nations still have much abundance of resources they can sustain their development. Especially in the era where we are talking about sustainable development, it is necessary to show high economic is not necessarily mean development so check the growth pattern and volume for resource sustainable. If we restrict trade by some amount the transfer of real national income can be restrained by some amount, the good pattern of growth can be achieve, and the environment would have low rate of degradation.

4. ANALYSIS OF VARIABLE

The correlation between the variables shows the inducement between them, one variable induces other variables to rise by the prior knowledge we can simply ink the direction & relation. That is if the economy

grows then the volume of trade becomes higher because of the increased production in the economy, rise in employment and per capita income. And the increased per capita income would lead to rise in import of the foreign products and the rising scale of production would make production cheaper and boost export & the worst part of the process is running the environment out of resources. The increased trade opens up the economy gives rise to expand the industry's output, providing choices of the variety of products, providing opportunities to large no of investors to invest and then gives rise to technological progress which works as a multiplier for the extraction of the resources. In the one hand the extraction process is in progress and on the other serious environmental problems arising due to the climate change.

In the following table the data shows the 10yr later of the trade liberalization and before 10 year of the trade liberalization to compare the amount of the carbon emission & economic growth, Economic growth & trade volume and carbon emission & trade volume before the economic reform 1991 and after the reform. In the table we have to analyze the absolute amount of the particular variable and also increase in the absolute amount. The relation can be here established by prior knowledge is trade and economic growth induces each other to increase but doesn't mean they are the only factor effecting; they are one of the large no. of factor affecting. But the carbon emission is a function of the economic growth is directly related also. The trade induces growth so by putting this in dilemma we can conclude trade also induces the carbon to rise. If the openness trade is grater that means the carbon emission is also greater.

A. PRE TRADE LIBERALIZATION 1971-80

YEAR	A GDP _{PPP} PER CAPITA	B TRADE VOLUME	C CO ₂
1971	119	5.17	0.36
1972	123	5.53	0.37
1973	144	7.64	0.38
1974	163	10.8	0.38
1975	158	12.11	0.40
1976	161	13.15	0.41
1977	186	16.36	0.43
1978	206	17.72	0.42
1979	224	22.83	0.43
1980	267	28.67	0.45

B. POSTTRADE LIBERALIZATION 2001-2010

YEAR	A GDP _{PPP} PER CAPITA	B TRADE VOLUME	C CO ₂
2001	452	126.18	0.97
2002	471	151.95	0.96
2003	547	185.91	0.99
2004	628	265.96	1.02
2005	715	344.58	1.06
2006	807	429.93	1.12
2007	1028	553.88	1.19
2008	999	639.83	1.31
2009	1102	620.93	1.43
2010	1358	825.32	1.43

Data source: www.macrotrends.net , GDP per capita in US \$, Trade volume in US Billion \$, CO2 per capita in metric ton

In India during these year the unprecedented population had grown, so by taking care of this the data has been chosen for per capita values of the variable which is possible. After having a look on the above both table we may have the say that, the per capita GDP in the year 1971 is 119\$ after 5 year in 1976 there has been a increase of 42\$ and in 1980 the total increase from 1971 to 1980 is 148 \$ this was before trade liberalization. In the after the trade openness from 2001 to 2010 the increment in GDP per capita is 906\$ all most triple of the former. The increment only in the GDP of 10 year of the case B is half of the total of case A. Let's analyze the trade volume before the trade 1971-80the volume of trade can be found to be very steady and slow rate of growth in 1971, 5.17 billion \$ in after 5 year in 1976 the volume becomes 13.15 B \$, and in the year 1980 28.67 B \$. But if we compare this with 2002-2010 the case A seems negligible in front of B the total

growth in trade volume in case of A in 23.5 B \$. In the later decade it is 699.14 billion dollar. However they both are inducing each other but there are many other factors who are affecting these two variables but in our study is confined with only with this variable.

The main concern of the study is the carbon emission which was almost constant in the case, because in that time the per capita growth of GDP was less and the volume of trade was also less, in the latter case we can see the sharp increase in the carbon emission at the same time the growth in GDP and volume of trade also can be seen. Like in 1971 to 1980 the total increase was limited between 0.09 metric tons fluctuations if we make an average growth of 0.009 annually. But in the latter case it goes up from 0.97 metric ton to 1.43 metric ton the total rise was 0.46 metric ton per capita. We can't deny the fact that at this time the growth in trade volume and GDP was also very high. No doubt the carbon emission is a direct function of economic growth but somewhere economic growth is a function of trade volume, that means indirectly direct relation between carbon emission and trade volume exists.

The above per capita data might seem very insignificant in nature but the amount of environmental degradation can be imagined by seeing the total carbon emission. In the thirty year of the economic processing from 1960 to 1990 the rise in emission is 498572.66 kilo tons of CO₂ we can't even imagine the amount of pollution that is only by one country and degradation of environment, this was the growth only if we sum all the year how large would be the emission. The pre trade liberalization pollution was

high and we know the amount of loss but if we compare the amount of post liberalization the devastation can be visualized, that is from the economic reform in 1991 the amount of emission is 6,58,189.83 kilo tons to 2407671.53 kilo tons of emission in the year 2016 only. And the growth in the 26 year is 1749481.7 kilo tons. This is just shocking and frightful.. The above diagram shows the growth in emission before globalization is very low as compared to post globalization.

5. THE SDGs and TRADE OPENNESS:

By the above study it can be presumed that high degree of trade openness induces the carbon emission to rise and also economic growth also. So the economic growth, is not responsive economic development by full amount, and it does not consider the economic inequality rather economic inequality increases up to certain amount as economic growth happens the environmental Kuznets curves support the statement. And also we can't achieve our Envision 2030 how let's see

Goal 10 reduced inequality above study shows the inequality increases with high growth and with this G.1 No poverty, G.2 zero hunger can't be achieved. Due to the growing environmental degradation (CO₂ emission) the target of G.6 clean water sanitation, G.12 responsible consumption and production, G.13 climate action, G.14 life below water, G.15 life on land can't be full filled. Even if the goal achieved up to 2030 then the long term growth of sustainable growth can't be maintained for long period of time because we're talking about the sustainable development.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The development of international trade is a very holistic approach for the human being to optimize the use or efficient utilization of global resources as a whole but at the same time it has some bad side which is the matter of discussion in this study. All the above analysis and studies of data is to show that the trade openness is a major factor to economic growth and environmental degradation. The tables given above shows the pre and post trade liberalization data by which we can conclude that in the post trade

liberalization period the environmental degradation is very high and the rate of growth in absolute term is also very high. If the degree of trade openness is very high economic growth is stimulated and the pattern of consumption and production also changes, the economy started producing the luxurious product where the waste of economic resources are high. If we talk about sustained growth both process are exactly contradictory. And finally if we talk about the goals of sustainable development goals a lots of objective will remained if the process continues in this way. The for controlling trade openness some suggestions are given below why and how should be.

7. SUGGESTIONS

. Of course we do not have any problem with the economic growth; we've the problem of pattern of growth because the high rate of economic growth does not necessarily shows economic development in the SDGs analysis shows that economic growth increases inequality, and the definition of the development induced by economic growth is not fit for this era of 21st century because the old development definitions says "development means providing huge amount of choices to the people for increasing their standard of living". In my point of view old development is more of a wastage of economic resource, in my frame of references the "economic development should give a healthy living to all the people over a sustained period of time" in my view development should be inclusive and sustainable as long as possible which means the real development of the economy and it's resources the former one shows only development of human not the economic development. And for the sustained growth the rate doesn't need to be so high and for controlling the growth and increasing economic development, the competition prevailing between the nations are need to be under controlled. There should be some amount of trade restrictions and that too different for different economy. And mostly one of the non-economic factor that is global peace is needed so that the pace of competition for economic power will be lower, then only the people would think of

development of humanity and inclusivity
of all kinds of lives.

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